

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE BLOCH SEMINORMS OF A HARMONIC MAPPING AND THE BLOCH SEMINORMS OF THE ASSOCIATED REAL AND IMAGINARY PARTS

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Abstract

In this paper, we introduce Bloch space \mathcal{B}_H as the space of functions f which is analytic in the unit disc \mathbb{D} such that $(1 - |z|^2)f'(z)$ is bounded. We presented some theorems associated with Banach harmonic space and harmonic Bloch norm. We get the relationship between the Bloch seminorms of a harmonic mapping and the Bloch seminorms of the associated real and imaginary parts.

Keywords: Banach Space, Bloch Space \mathcal{B}_H , Harmonic Mapping.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the mathematical field of complex analysis, the Bloch space, named after French mathematician André Bloch and denoted \mathcal{B} . A function f analytic in the unit disk \mathbb{D} belongs to the Bloch space

$$\|f\|_{\mathcal{B}} = \sup_{z \in \mathbb{D}} (1 - |z|^2)|f'(z)| < \infty. \quad (1)$$

See [23]. If we identify functions that differ by a constant, then \mathcal{B} becomes a Banach space with norm (1), and \mathcal{B}_0 is a closed subspace of \mathcal{B} . The classical theory of Bloch functions in the open unit disk \mathbb{D} and the interesting connections between the Bloch space \mathcal{B} and other function spaces has led to many new areas of research in the past two decades. Bloch functions play an important role in the interaction between geometric function and operator theory. They are often viewed as symbols of bounded Hankel operators. See [4,7,8,9,11,12,14,20,21].

It is well known that a harmonic mapping h admits a representation of the form $f+g$, where f and g are analytic functions. This representation is unique if, fixing a base point z_0 , the function g is chosen so that $g(z_0) = 0$. Banach spaces are named after the Polish mathematician Stefan Banach, who introduced this concept and studied it systematically in 1920–1922 along with Hans Hahn and Eduard Helly. In mathematics, more specifically in functional analysis, a Banach space is a complete normed vector space.

The vector space structure allows one to relate the behavior of Cauchy sequences to that of converging series of vectors. Every Banach space is a Baire space, although there exist normed spaces that are Baire but not Banach. In the last several decades, much research has been carried out on the study of Banach spaces of analytic functions on the open unit disk \mathbb{D} in the complex plane.

Since analytic functions are clearly harmonic [3,6,8,9,10,12,13,17,18,19]. This study is arranged as follows. In section 2, we present some notations of harmonic Bloch space. In section 3, we introduce some theorems associated with Banach harmonic space and harmonic Bloch norm. In section 4 we present the little harmonic Bloch space $\mathcal{B}_{H,0}$.

2. PRELIMINARIES

We recall the harmonic Bloch space as the set \mathcal{B}_H consisting of all complex-valued harmonic Bloch mappings on \mathbb{D} . It is straightforward to see that the mapping $h \mapsto \beta_h$ is a semi norm known as the Bloch semi norm, which is not a norm since it does not distinguish the constant functions [1, 2,8,9,12,15,16].

Definition 1. Let h be a harmonic mapping on \mathbb{D} . The mapping h is called Bloch if it satisfies the Lipschitz condition when regarded as a mapping from the hyperbolic disk into \mathbb{C} . That is, there exists a constant $c \geq 0$ such that

$$|h(z)h(w) \leq c\rho(zw)| \quad \text{for all } z, w \in \mathbb{D}.$$

If this condition holds for h , the greatest lower bound of all such constants c is called the Lipschitz number of h and denoted by L_h . Equivalently, the Lipschitz number of h can be described as

$$L_h = \sup_{z \neq w} \frac{|h(z)-h(w)|}{\rho(zw)}$$

And

$$\beta_h := \sup_{z \in \mathbb{D}} (1 - |z|^2)|h'(z)| < \infty$$

where the supremum is taken over all pairs of distinct points z and w in \mathbb{D} , and $\beta_h = L_h$. If h is a Bloch harmonic mapping represented as $h = f + \bar{g}$, with f and g analytic in \mathbb{D} , the Bloch semi norm of h can be described as

$$\beta_h := \sup_{z \in \mathbb{D}} (1 - |z|^2)|f'(z)| + |g'(z)|.$$

A Bloch harmonic mapping can be characterized by means of its complex gradient, namely, a harmonic mapping h is Bloch if and only if

$$\sup_{z \in \mathbb{D}} (1 - |z|^2)(|h_z(z)| + |h_{\bar{z}}(z)|) \tag{2}$$

it is finite.

Theorem 1 [22]. $h \in \mathcal{B}_H$ if and only if f and g are in \mathcal{B} .

Furthermore,

$$\max\{\mathcal{B}_f, \mathcal{B}_g\} \leq \mathcal{B}_h \leq \mathcal{B}_f + \mathcal{B}_g.$$

Theorem 2 [22]. Let h be a bound harmonic mapping on \mathbb{D} . Then $\beta_h \leq \frac{4}{\pi} \|h\|_\infty$.

For $h \in \mathcal{B}_H$, $h = f + \bar{g} \in H(\mathbb{D})$ satisfying the normalization condition $g(0) = 0$.

Definition 2. The little harmonic Bloch space $\mathcal{B}_{H,0}$ is the set of all harmonic Bloch mappings as follows:

$$\mathcal{B}_{H,0} = \left\{ h \in \mathcal{B}_H : \lim_{|z| \rightarrow 1} (1 - |z|^2)(|h_z(z)| + |h_{\bar{z}}(z)|) = 0 \right\}.$$

Note that $h = f + \bar{g} \in \mathcal{B}_{H,0}$ with $f, g \in \mathcal{B}_0$.

3. ALTERNATIVE DESCRIPTION OF β_h

Formula (2) gives an alternative description of β_h . Indeed, from the representation

$h = f + \bar{g}$, with $f, g \in H(\mathbb{D})$, differentiating with respect to z and \bar{z} separately, we see that $h_z = f'$ and $h_{\bar{z}} = \bar{g}'$. Since for a real-valued harmonic function h

$$|h_z| + |h_{\bar{z}}| = \frac{1}{2}|h_x - ih_y| + \frac{1}{2}|h_x + ih_y| = (h_x^2 + h_y^2)^{\frac{1}{2}},$$

an alternative expression for the seminorm of a real-valued harmonic Bloch function h is

$$\beta_h = \sup_{z \in \mathbb{D}} (1 - |z|^2) \|\nabla h(z)\|, \quad (3)$$

where $\nabla h = (h_x, h_y)$ and the norm is the Euclidean norm in the plane. (3) For an analytic function, this definition agrees with the well-known condition defining a Bloch function.

Remark 1. Since the real and imaginary parts of an analytic function are real-valued harmonic functions, analytic and antianalytic functions are harmonic mappings. Therefore, \mathcal{B} is a subspace of \mathcal{B}_H .

4. REAL PART AND THE IMAGINARY PART OF AN ANALYTIC FUNCTION f

Theorem 3. If h is the real part or the imaginary part of an analytic function f , then

$$\beta_h = \beta_f.$$

In particular, $h \in \mathcal{B}_H$ if and only if $f \in \mathcal{B}$.

Proof. Let $h = \operatorname{Re} f$, then h can be written as $h = \frac{1}{2}(f + \bar{f})$. Thus

$$\beta_h = \sup_{z \in \mathbb{D}} (1 - |z|^2) \left(\frac{1}{2}|f'(z)| + \frac{1}{2}|f'(z)| \right) = \sup_{z \in \mathbb{D}} (1 - |z|^2)|f'(z)| = \beta_f.$$

Likewise, if $h = \operatorname{Im} f$, then h can be written as $h = \frac{1}{2i}f - \frac{1}{2i}\bar{f}$. Therefore

$$\beta_f = \sup_{z \in \mathbb{D}} (1 - |z|^2) \left(\frac{1}{2}|f'(z)| + \frac{1}{2}|f'(z)| \right) = \sup_{z \in \mathbb{D}} (1 - |z|^2)|f'(z)| = \beta_h.$$

Remark 3. The correspondence $h \rightarrow \beta_h$ is invariant under right composition by conformal automorphism of \mathbb{D} . Furthermore, as shown the harmonic mapping h is Bloch if and only if the unique functions f and g analytic on \mathbb{D} such that $h = f + \bar{g}$ with $g(0) = 0$ are Bloch.

5. RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE BLOCH SEMINORMS OF A HARMONIC MAPPING AND THE BLOCH SEMINORMS

Lemma 1. Let h be harmonic on \mathbb{D} and let $u = \operatorname{Re} h$ and $v = \operatorname{Im} h$. Then, $h \in \mathcal{B}_H$ if and only if $u, v \in \mathcal{B}_H$. Moreover

$$\frac{1}{4}(\|u\|_{\mathcal{B}_H} + \|v\|_{\mathcal{B}_H}) \leq \|h\|_{\mathcal{B}_H} \leq \|u\|_{\mathcal{B}_H} + \|v\|_{\mathcal{B}_H}. \quad (4)$$

Proof. Assume first that $u, v \in \mathcal{B}_H$. Then, by linearity, $h \in \mathcal{B}_H$ and the upper estimate follows immediately from the triangle inequality of the norm. To prove the lower estimate, assume $h \in \mathcal{B}_H$ and observe that setting

$$J(u, v) = u_x v_y - v_x u_y$$

Then, we get

$$2|J(u, v)| \leq \|\nabla u\|^2 + \|\nabla v\|^2,$$

Where $\nabla u = (u_x, u_y)$ and $\nabla v = (v_x, v_y)$ then, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & (\|\nabla u\|^2 + \|\nabla v\|^2 + 2J(u, v))^{\frac{1}{2}} + (\|\nabla u\|^2 + \|\nabla v\|^2 - 2J(u, v))^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ & \geq \sqrt{2}(\|\nabla u\|^2 + \|\nabla v\|^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Squaring L.H.S of Eq. (4) we deduce

$$\begin{aligned} & (\|\nabla u\|^2 + \|\nabla v\|^2 + 2J(u, v)) + (\|\nabla u\|^2 + \|\nabla v\|^2 - 2J(u, v)) \\ & \geq 2((\|\nabla u\|^2 + \|\nabla v\|^2)^2 - 4(J(u, v))^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} \end{aligned}$$

so cancelling opposite terms, neglecting the last term and combining like terms, we obtain $2(\|\nabla u\|^2 + \|\nabla v\|^2)$, which is the square of the right-hand side of inequality (5) we may now compute $|h_z| + |h_{\bar{z}}|$ in terms of u and v by first expressing the partials with respect to z and \bar{z} in terms of the partials with respect to x and y , then computing the modulus and then finally applying inequality (5)

$$\begin{aligned} |h_z| + |h_{\bar{z}}| &= |u_z + iv_z| + |u_{\bar{z}} + iv_{\bar{z}}| \\ &= \frac{1}{2}|u_x - iu_y + i(v_x - iv_y)| + \frac{1}{2}|u_x + iu_y + i(v_x + iv_y)| \\ &= \frac{1}{2}|u_x + v_y + i(v_x - u_y)| + \frac{1}{2}|u_x - v_y + i(v_x + u_y)| \\ &= \frac{1}{2}((u_x + v_y)^2 + (v_x + u_y)^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{1}{2}((u_x - v_y)^2 + (v_x + u_y)^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &= \frac{1}{2}(\|\nabla u\|^2 + \|\nabla v\|^2 + 2J(u, v))^{\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{1}{2}(\|\nabla u\|^2 + \|\nabla v\|^2 - 2J(u, v))^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &\geq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\|\nabla u\|^2 + \|\nabla v\|^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\geq \frac{1}{2}(\|\nabla u\| + \|\nabla v\|),$$

Where in the last step we used the inequality

$$\|(z_1, z_2)\| \geq \frac{|z_1|+|z_2|}{\sqrt{2}}, \text{ for } z_j \in \mathbb{C}, j = 1,2. \quad (6)$$

Therefore, multiplying by $(1 - |z|^2)$ and taking the supremum over all $z \in \mathbb{D}$ and recalling from expression (3), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \beta_h &= \sup_{z \in \mathbb{D}} (1 - |z|^2)(\|\nabla u(z)\| + \|\nabla v(z)\|) \\ &\geq \frac{1}{2} \max(\beta_u, \beta_v) \\ &\geq \frac{1}{4}(\beta_u, \beta_v). \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Now, using again inequality (6), we have

$$|h(0)| \geq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|u(0) + |v(0)||). \quad (8)$$

Combining (7) & (8), we get

$$\|h\|_{\mathcal{B}_H} \geq \frac{1}{4}(\|u\|_{\mathcal{B}_H} + \|v\|_{\mathcal{B}_H}),$$

proving that u and v are in \mathcal{B}_H , and the lower estimate holds.

We now show that the point evaluation estimates that holds for the classical Bloch space also holds for the harmonic Bloch space.

Theorem 4. For $h \in \mathcal{B}_H$ and $z \in \mathbb{D}$, there exist

$$|h(z)| \leq |h(0)| + \frac{1}{2} \log \frac{1 + |z|}{1 - |z|} \|h\|_{\mathcal{B}_H},$$

And hence

$$|h(z)| \leq \max \left\{ 1, \frac{1}{2} \log \frac{1+|z|}{1-|z|} \right\} \|h\|_{\mathcal{B}_H}.$$

Proof. Let $h \in \mathcal{B}_H$ and $z \in \mathbb{D}$. The inequality is clear for $z = 0$. Assume $z \neq 0$. Then, by the triangle inequality, the definition of Bloch seminorm, and the formula of the hyperbolic distance, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |h(z)| &\leq |h(0)| + |h(z) - h(0)| \\ &= |h(0)| + \frac{|h(z)-h(0)|}{\rho(z,0)} \\ &\leq |h(0)| + \beta_h \rho(z, 0) \\ &= |h(0)| + (\|h\|_{\mathcal{B}_H} - |h(0)|)\rho(z, 0) \\ &= (1 - \rho(z, 0))|h(0)| + \rho(z, 0)\|h\|_{\mathcal{B}_H} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \max\{1, \rho(z, 0)\} \|h\|_{\mathcal{B}_H} \\
 &= \max\left\{1, \frac{1}{2} \log \frac{1+|z|}{1-|z|}\right\} \|h\|_{\mathcal{B}_H}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Which completes the proof.

Corollary 1. For $h \in \mathcal{B}_H$ and $\varphi \in S(\mathbb{D})$, then

$$|h(\varphi(0))| \leq |h(0)| + \frac{1}{2} \log \frac{1 + |h(0)|}{1 - |h(0)|} \beta_h.$$

Remark 2. For $h = f + \bar{g}$ with $f, g \in H(\mathbb{D})$, we define h to be Bloch type function if

$$b_h = \sup_{z \in \mathbb{D}} (1 - |z|^2) \sqrt{|J_h(z)|} < \infty$$

Where $J_h(z)$ is the Jacobian of h at z , namely

$$J_h(z) = |f'(z)|^2 - |g'(z)|^2$$

Where the analytic function f is assumed to be locally univalent. It is evident that in this case

$$\sqrt{|J_h(z)|} \leq |f'(z)| + |g'(z)| = |h_z(z)| + |h_{\bar{z}}(z)|.$$

Thus

$$b_h = \sup_{z \in \mathbb{D}} (1 - |z|^2) \sqrt{|J_h(z)|} \leq \sup_{z \in \mathbb{D}} (1 - |z|^2) (|h_z(z)| + |h_{\bar{z}}(z)|) = \beta_h.$$

Acknowledgment

The authors extend their appreciation to Umm Al-Qura University, Saudi Arabia for funding this research through grant number: 25UQU4310382GSSR03.

Funding statement

This research work was funded by Umm Al-Qura University, Saudi Arabia under grant under: 25UQU4310382GSSR03.

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